

Factors Affecting Beta-decay Life-time of Ground State of the Isotopes

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Abstract: The variation of β -decay life-time of the ground state of various isotope chains is studied. The life time of the ground states displays a systematic behaviour with respect to the ratio of the number of neutron holes and the maximum possible number of neutron holes in that shell. Lifetime of the ground states depending on the particle or hole nature of the protons and neutrons, as well as whether they belong to the same shell or not, are found to exhibit similar increasing or decreasing trends. An empirical relation between the lifetime and the parameter is suggested for odd Z and even $(Z\pm 1)$ nuclei.

Keywords: half-life, β -decay, isotopes

1. Introduction

The various properties of the nuclei have correlation with the number of valence nucleons. The role of neutron-proton interaction in the growth of deformation away from shell closures and importance of the $N_p N_n$ parameterization was first demonstrated by Casten [1–4]. The N_p and N_n stands for the number of valence particles/holes for the protons and neutrons respectively. It was considered that, if the number of valence nucleons lie below the middle of a major shell, they are considered as particles; otherwise they are taken to be holes. A correlation between ground state lifetime and valence nucleon particles/holes for isotopic chains has been discussed in Ref [5]. Various nuclear properties such as

rotational moments, deformation, core cluster decomposition, mean field binding energy and alpha-decay spectroscopic factors follow simple trends, when expressed as a function of N_p and N_n or certain function of N_p and N_n . The simple relationship between the ground state energies of even-even nuclei spanning a wide region of mass (from mass number 76 to 254), equilibrium shape, and their valence nucleon numbers (N_p and N_n) was shown in the Refs [6,7]. This relationship enabled us to deduce much useful information about the equilibrium shape of an articular nucleus just from the knowledge of its energy and to predict the excitation energies of even-even nuclei belonging to this mass region with reasonable accuracy [8–10].

The systematics of nuclear deformation for even-even, even-odd, odd-even, and doubly odd nuclei in four regions: the $50 < Z \leq 66$ and $82 < Z \leq 104$ region, the $66 < Z \leq 82$ and $82 < Z \leq 104$ region, the $66 < Z \leq 82$ and $104 < Z \leq 126$ region, and the $82 < Z \leq 104$ and $126 < Z \leq 155$ region were presented in the Refs [11–13]. Compact trajectories were obtained using the $P = \frac{N_p N_n}{N_p + N_n}$ factor. It was found that there were no apparent shifts in the trajectories between the even-even nuclei previously studied with the P factor. It was also suggested that the pairing interaction strength of even-even nuclei is very close to that in their odd A and doubly odd neighbours. Strong anomalies around the $Z = 80$ region were highlighted in the Refs [3, 4, 11–16].

In the present work, we have shown the effects of number of valence particles/holes and the number of nucleons (protons and neutrons) on the life-time of the ground state of isotopes. To show the dependence of life-time on the number of valence particles/holes and the number of nucleons, we have introduced two parameters, namely δ_ν and δ_π . The former (δ_ν) is the difference in the valence neutron particle/holes between the parent and daughter nuclei, the later (δ_π) is difference in the number of protons between the parent and daughter nuclei. An empirical relation between life-time and parameter (δ_π) is also suggested for odd and even nuclei. The experimental data used in this work is taken from the ENSDF database [17]. As ground state decay contains nuclear structure effects, and may be thought to depend on the overlap between the actual ground state configuration of the parent and the configuration of the daughter states. Therefore, besides other quantities, lifetime should depend on the number of nucleon valence particles/holes, number of neutrons/protons, as well as whether they are in same shell or not, in the parent and daughter nucleus. The β -decay (β^- or/and β^+) lifetime of the ground state of various isotope chains is plotted against the parameter, ξ [18] defined as,

$$\xi = \frac{N_n}{(N_n)_{max}} \quad (1)$$

Where, for a chain of isotopes, $(N_n)_{max}$ is calculated by taking the maximum N_n value [5, 19, 20] for the chain, which corresponds to number of particles/holes at the middle of a shell. This normalized value of ξ represents the fraction of the integrated proton-neutron interaction [1–4] with respect to the

maximum value in the chain of isotopes for a given shell. Similar modifications of the $N_p N_n$ scheme have been discussed in the Refs [7, 21].

2. Results and Discussions

In the present work, our main motive is to find any previously unnoticed smooth variation in the β -decay lifetime of ground state i.e. variation in the stability with the parameter ξ . In the ref [18] efforts were made by the authors toward a unified $N_p N_n$ treatment for the lifetime of ground state. In this work, we present a more comprehensive picture and suggest an empirical relation.

In Figure 1, we present the half-life values of the ground state of β -emitters for a number of isotopes as a function of the parameter ξ . The half-life values of the ground state of β -emitter are from the ENSDF database. To keep the figures easily readable, we have included only certain elements in the region $Z = 30-80$, though we find that other elements also follow a similar behavior. Later, while discussing the trends in more detail, we will choose certain regions and discuss the trends for almost all the nuclei in them.

Fig. 1: (Colour online) The half-life values of ground states of nuclei for different valence regions in various chains of isotopes. The atomic number (Z) of isotopic chains are indicated in the figure. The lines are only for guiding the eye.

We find that the lifetimes of ground states evolve smoothly with respect to the parameter ξ with different trends for different valence regions. Individually, curves of various observables for different valence regions (P-P, H-H, P-H,P-P_d, H-P_d, H-H_d) of all the isotopes of many elements, appear in a narrow band or envelope, thus providing a unifying framework for understanding the systematic behavior. In our notation, P and H refer to particle and hole type nucleons, respectively. The suffix d indicate that valence protons and neutrons are in different shells. The values of the parameter ξ for an isotopic chain in various valence regions can easily be understood from the few representative examples presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Examples of isotopes ranges in different valence regions for the isotopic chains of Te, Zr, Zn, Sr and Cd.

Valence Regions	Isotope Range	N_p	$(N_n)_{max}$	N_n	ξ
P-P	$^{102}_{52}Te_{50}$ $^{102}_{52}Te_{66}$	2P	16 P	0 16 P	0 1
H-H	$^{90}_{40}Zr_{50}$ $^{80}_{40}Zr_{40}$	10H	10 H	0 10 H	0 1
P-H	$^{80}_{30}Zn_{50}$ $^{70}_{30}Zn_{40}$	2 P	10 H	0 10 H	0 1
P-P _d	$^{88}_{38}Sr_{50}$ $^{104}_{38}Sr_{66}$	10 P	16 P _d	0 16 P _d	0 1
H-P _d	$^{104}_{48}Cd_{66}$ $^{104}_{48}Cd_{60}$	2 H	16 P _d	0 16 P _d	0 1
H-H _d	$^{130}_{48}Cd_{82}$ $^{116}_{48}Cd_{68}$	2 H	16 H _d	0 16 H _d	0 1

We have shown that in a particular beta decay, lifetime of the ground states of the isotopic chains behaves in a systematic manner with respect to simple parameters (ξ, η). The ground state lifetime increases smoothly with ξ for (P-P, P-H, H-P_d, H-H_d) valence regions and decreases smoothly for (P-P_d, H-H) regions. The curves for a particular valence region also look similar. Such a behavior of lifetime of nuclear states has not been previously noted, except a correlation which has been demonstrated between $N_p N_n$ and E2 hindrance factors, for details see Ref [22].

The lifetime patterns in Fig 1, behaved in a systematic way with respect to ξ depending on the nature of the decay. It is seen that a particular region exhibits similar trends (rising or falling) with the parameter ξ (see Fig 1). Naturally, it would be useful to find some parameter or quantity shared by all the regions showing a similar trend.

A. Role of number of valence particles/holes

The ground state decay contains nuclear structure effects, and may be thought to depend on the overlap between the actual ground state configuration of the parent and the configuration of the daughter states. Therefore, besides other quantities, lifetime should depend on the number of neutrons/protons, as well as whether particle-like or hole-like in parent and daughter nucleus. Now the change in the N_n value depends on the way a nucleus decays, either (Electron Capture / β^+) or (β^-), as well as whether neutrons are particle-like or hole-like. We observe that the difference in valence neutron particle/hole numbers between the parent and the daughter, $\delta_v = N_n^d - N_n^p$, has the character that it is the same for all the nuclei showing a similar trend. The values of this quantity for various valence regions have been given in the fourth column of Table II. It is clear that a value of +1 (-1) corresponds to increase (decrease) of lifetime with ξ . But at the same time, we also observe that difference in valence proton particle/hole numbers between the parent and the daughter $\delta_\pi = N_p^p - N_p^d$ has the no character (see Table 2). The values of this quantity for various valence regions have been given in the fifth column of Table 2.

Table 2: Trends of lifetime in different valence regions, decay mode and the quantity δ_v, δ_π . See text for details.

Valence Regions	Decay Mode	Trend with ξ	$\delta_v = N_n^d - N_n^p$	$\delta_\pi = N_p^p - N_p^d$
P-P	EC/ β^+	Increasing	+1	+1
H-H	EC/ β^+	Decreasing	-1	-1
P-H	β^-	Increasing	+1	+1
P-P _d	β^-	Decreasing	-1	+1
P-H _d	β^-	Increasing	+1	+1
H-P _d	EC/ β^+	Increasing	+1	-1 No
H-H _d	β^-	Increasing	+1	-1 No

B. Role of number of protons/neutrons

In the previous subsection, we have seen the effect of valence particles/holes on the lifetime of the ground states of the isotope chain. Now to see the effect of number of neutrons/protons in parent and daughter nucleus on the half-life of the isotopes, we introduce a new quantity η defined as

$$\eta = \delta_v \frac{N_n}{(N_n)_{max}} \tag{2}$$

. The half-life of the ground state of the isotope chain is plotted against quantity η . Figure 2 shows the variation of lifetime of isotopic chains with quantity η . A close observation of the life-time patterns

shows that, in case of EC/ β^+ decay, lifetime of odd-Z nuclei and even-(Z+1) nuclei (provided both nuclei have same number of neutrons: isotones) are almost same, while in case of β^- , the lifetime of odd-Z nuclei and even-(Z-1) nuclei(isotones) is nearly same.

As we have observed that, in case of EC// β^+ decay, lifetime of odd-Z nuclei and even-(Z+1) nuclei are almost same, while in case of β^- , the lifetime of odd-Z nuclei and even-(Z-1) nuclei(isotones) is nearly same. So the expected empirical relation between lifetime of odd-Z and even-(Z \pm 1) nuclei is as, $\tau_z \sim \tau_z + \delta_\pi$. An example of isotones with close by lifetime is given in table 3.

Table 3: Isotones ($\tau_z \sim \tau_z + \delta_\pi$) having nearly same beta-decay lifetimes

Valence regions	Decay Mode	δ_π	Isotones			
			τ_z	Half-life	$\tau_z + \delta_\pi$	Half -life
H-H	EC/ β^+	+1	$^{83}_{41}Nb$	3.80 sec	$^{84}_{42}Mo$	2.30 sec
			$^{85}_{41}Nb$	20.50 sec	$^{86}_{42}Mo$	19.10 sec
			$^{87}_{41}Nb$	3.75 min	$^{88}_{42}Mo$	8.00 min
			$^{89}_{41}Nb$	2.03 hour	$^{90}_{42}Mo$	5.56 hour
H-P _d	EC/ β^+	+1	$^{163}_{71}Lu$	3.97 min	$^{164}_{72}Hf$	1.85 min
			$^{165}_{71}Lu$	10.74 min	$^{166}_{72}Hf$	6.77 min
			$^{167}_{71}Lu$	51.5 min	$^{168}_{72}Hf$	25.95 min
			$^{169}_{71}Lu$	34.06 min	$^{170}_{72}Hf$	16.01 hour
P-P _d	β^-	-1	$^{143}_{57}La$	14.20 min	$^{142}_{56}Ba$	10.60 min
			$^{145}_{57}La$	24.80 sec	$^{144}_{56}Ba$	11.50 sec
			$^{147}_{57}La$	4.06 sec	$^{146}_{56}Ba$	2.22 sec
H-H _d	β^-	-1	$^{179}_{71}Lu$	4.59 Hour	$^{178}_{70}Yb$	1.23 hour
			$^{181}_{71}Lu$	3.5 min	$^{180}_{70}Yb$	2.4 min

Fig. 2: (Colour online) The lifetime of odd-even nuclei (τ_z) close to even-even nuclei ($\tau_z + \delta_\pi$). The lines are only for guiding the eye.

4. Conclusion

The trends observed in life-times of ground states of various isotopes in different valence regions can be easily under-stand by the knowledge of number of nucleon valence particles/holes, number of neutrons/protons, as well as whether they are in same shell or not, in the parent and daughter nucleus. This indicates that it may perhaps be possible to obtain simple prescriptions for lifetime estimates with ξ and η as parameters. This is merely a general trend, as the factors like energy, spin-parity and configuration of the parent state and the daughter state(s), the forbidden-ness of the decay, etc. have strong impact on the nature of the decay. The β -decay lifetime values for ground states of a large number of isotopes are seen to exhibit simple variations with the ratio of the numbers of valence neutrons (particles or holes) and the maximum possible valence neutrons in medium. The variations display distinct and unique trends in different valence regions. We observe that the difference in valence neutron particle/hole numbers between the parent and the daughter has the character that it is the same for all the nuclei showing a similar trend. But difference in valence proton particle/hole numbers between the parent and the daughter has the no character. The lifetimes of ground state of odd-Z nuclei and even- ($Z\pm 1$) nuclei are seen to exhibit a close relationship.

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